

Terms of Reference of EIA Study for Meghnaghat Power Station

**Dhaka School
of Economics**

Terms of Reference of EIA Study for Meghnaghat Power Station

Submitted by

Name: Shakil Khan

ID: 02

Semester: 06 Batch: 05

Session: 2019-2020

Submitted to

Masud Iqbal Md. Shameem, PhD

Director

Department of Environment

Course Title: Environmental Impact Assessment

Course Code: C – 306

Date of Submission: February 08, 2024

1. Name and address of entrepreneur

Meghnaghat Power Station

Level-3-4; Bangabandhu Bhaban,

Meghnaghat, Gazaria, Munshiganj-1525.

Consultant for ESIA Study

Centre for Environment and Geographic Information Services (CEGIS)

House #6, Rd- 23/C, G ulshan-1, Dhaka 1212

2. Survey Team

The composition of the study team is given below.

SL	Discipline	Qualifications and Tasks
a	Team Leader: Afzal Hussain, PhD	<ul style="list-style-type: none">➤ Working under the ministry of Environment for the last 16 years.➤ Completed his PhD in Environmental Management from the University of Oxford.➤ Additionally, Mr. Afzal is has working experience with more than 25 different projects.
b	Water Resources Specialist: Dr. Munaf Khan	<ul style="list-style-type: none">➤ Working under the ministry of Water Resource in Bangladesh for the last 9 years.➤ Completed his PhD in Civil and Water Engineering from Indian Institute of Technology Madras.
c	Sociologist: Dr. Fahmid Karim	<ul style="list-style-type: none">➤ Working as a Professor in the University of Dhaka for the last 4 years.➤ Completed his PhD in Sociology from London School Economics and Political Science.
d	Ecologist: Dr. Bushra Moni	<ul style="list-style-type: none">➤ Working as an Ecologist in BRAC.➤ Completed her PhD in Ecology from University of Leicester.
e	Climate Change and Disaster Risk Management Specialist: M. K. M. Mukul Uddin	<ul style="list-style-type: none">➤ Working as a Climate Specialist in UN.➤ Completed his PhD in Climate Change from the University of Cambridge.

Table: Survey Team

3. Needs of the Project:

Bangladesh's developmental trajectory relies heavily on ensuring a reliable and sustainable energy supply to fuel economic growth and achieve its ambitious socio-economic targets. The Government of Bangladesh (GoB), in alignment with its overarching vision for national progress, has embarked on a strategic journey towards elevating the country's status to an Upper Middle-Income Country (UMIC) by 2031 and ultimately attaining High-Income Country (HIC) status by 2041.

Given the nation's rapid industrialization and urbanization, there is a pressing need to address the escalating demand for electricity. The proposed establishment of a 2x660 MW diesel-based combined cycle power generation facility at Meghnaghat, Gazaria, Munshiganj, emerges as a vital initiative to meet this burgeoning energy demand while ensuring environmental sustainability and socio-economic development.

Meghnaghat, Gazaria, Munshiganj, chosen as the project site, offers strategic advantages for energy infrastructure development. Its proximity to major urban centers, including the capital city of Dhaka, and access to transportation networks make it an ideal location for establishing a power generation facility. Furthermore, the area's existing infrastructure and proximity to fuel supply routes enhance the feasibility and efficiency of the proposed project.

The proposed power generation facility is not only essential for addressing the immediate energy needs of Bangladesh but also plays a pivotal role in advancing the government's agenda of promoting regional development and economic diversification. By harnessing modern combined cycle technology, the project aims to maximize energy efficiency and minimize environmental impact, aligning with the nation's commitment to sustainable development.

Moreover, the establishment of the 2x660 MW power generation facility will contribute significantly to job creation, both during the construction phase and through operational employment opportunities. This will not only enhance the livelihoods of local communities but also stimulate economic growth in the region, in line with the government's vision of creating employment opportunities and fostering inclusive development.

In essence, the proposed diesel-based combined cycle power generation facility at Meghnaghat, Gazaria, Munshiganj, addresses the critical need for expanding Bangladesh's energy infrastructure to support economic growth and achieve its long-term developmental objectives. By ensuring a reliable and sustainable energy supply, the project serves as a catalyst for socio-economic progress and contributes to the nation's journey towards prosperity and self-sufficiency.

4. Project Concept:

The proposed 2x660 MW diesel-based combined cycle power generation facility at Meghnaghat, Gazaria, Munshiganj, embodies a pivotal initiative aimed at addressing Bangladesh's burgeoning energy demands while fostering sustainable economic development. Situated strategically in the Meghnaghat region, the project revolves around the concept of augmenting the country's power generation capacity to support its growing industrial and urban landscape.

Bangladesh's economy, in its pursuit of achieving Upper Middle-Income Country (UMIC) status by 2031 and High-Income Country (HIC) status by 2041, necessitates a robust energy infrastructure capable of powering its ambitious growth trajectory. However, the current energy landscape faces challenges, including intermittent power supply and reliance on traditional energy sources. The proposed power generation facility seeks to mitigate these challenges by introducing a modern, efficient, and environmentally sustainable approach to electricity generation.

The Meghnaghat location offers strategic advantages for the project's implementation. Its proximity to key urban centers and industrial zones, including the capital city of Dhaka, positions it as a crucial hub for meeting the energy needs of diverse sectors, including manufacturing, commerce, and residential areas. Additionally, the area's access to fuel supply routes and existing infrastructure enhances the feasibility and efficiency of the proposed facility.

At the heart of the project concept lies the objective of establishing a state-of-the-art power generation facility equipped with advanced combined cycle technology. This approach not only maximizes energy efficiency but also minimizes environmental impact, aligning with Bangladesh's commitment to sustainable development and climate resilience. By harnessing diesel-based combined cycle technology, the facility ensures reliable and uninterrupted power supply, essential for driving industrial growth and supporting socio-economic progress.

The establishment of the 2x660 MW power generation facility at Meghnaghat represents a significant step towards enhancing energy security, promoting industrialization, and fostering economic diversification in Bangladesh. By providing a stable and sustainable energy supply, the project catalyzes investment opportunities, creates employment, and accelerates regional development, thereby contributing to the nation's journey towards prosperity and self-sufficiency.

In summary, the project concept revolves around the imperative of modernizing Bangladesh's energy infrastructure to meet the evolving needs of its dynamic economy. By harnessing cutting-edge technology and strategic location advantages, the proposed power generation facility at Meghnaghat, Gazaria, Munshiganj, embodies a transformative initiative poised to drive sustainable development and elevate Bangladesh's position on the global stage.

4.1. Study Area:

The proposed 2x660 MW diesel-based combined cycle power generation facility is located at Meghnaghat, Gazaria, Munshiganj, situated strategically within the region to optimize its operational efficiency and accessibility to key resources and infrastructure.

Location: The project site is specifically situated in the vicinity of Meghnaghat, Gazaria, Munshiganj, Bangladesh, a location chosen for its strategic advantages in terms of proximity to major urban centers and transportation networks. It is approximately 60 kilometers away from the Padma Multipurpose Bridge and 100 kilometers away from Moongla Port, facilitating ease of access to both domestic and international markets.

Characteristics: The land in the project area is characterized as low-lying with predominantly one-season cropping practices, indicating its suitability for industrial development with minimal disruption to agricultural activities. Currently, the area enjoys access to water and electricity supply, although there is no gas connectivity available. The project site primarily consists of privately owned land with limited settlements, providing ample space for the establishment of the power generation facility and associated infrastructure.

Connectivity: Positioned in the southwestern part of the country, the project site benefits from its direct connectivity to the capital city, Dhaka, via the Padma Multipurpose Bridge. This strategic location enhances accessibility and facilitates the transportation of equipment, fuel, and personnel, thereby optimizing the operational efficiency of the power generation facility.

Map Presentation: A detailed map showcasing the location of the proposed power generation facility at Meghnaghat, Gazaria, Munshiganj, is provided to illustrate its spatial context and proximity to key infrastructure such as transportation networks, water bodies, and urban centers. This map serves as a visual aid in understanding the project's geographical setting and its relationship with surrounding areas and resources.

Map: Gazaria, Munshiganj

Map: Gazaria, Munshiganj

5. Project Options:

For the proposed 2x660 MW diesel-based combined cycle power generation facility at Meghnaghat, Gazaria, Munshiganj, there are no alternative project options or sites under consideration. The selection of the project location has been finalized by the local administration in consultation with community stakeholders, based on careful deliberation and consideration of various factors.

The chosen site at Meghnaghat, Gazaria, Munshiganj, offers unique advantages and suitability for the establishment of the power generation facility. Factors such as proximity to key infrastructure, including transportation networks and urban centers, availability of necessary resources, and minimal environmental impact, have been taken into account in the site selection process.

Furthermore, extensive consultations with community stakeholders have ensured that local perspectives and concerns are adequately addressed in the decision-making process. The fixed project location reflects a consensus among relevant authorities and stakeholders regarding the most appropriate site for the proposed power generation facility.

6. Description of the Existing Environment:

The proposed site for the 2x660 MW diesel-based combined cycle power generation facility at Meghnaghat, Gazaria, Munshiganj, exhibits specific environmental characteristics that must be understood and accounted for in project planning and implementation.

Topography and Soil: The project site is slightly lower than the adjacent road, necessitating some filling of the site within the economic zone. The soil type is predominantly loamy, conducive to construction activities and infrastructure development.

Seismic Activity: Located in the southwest region of Bangladesh, the site falls within a low-seismic activity zone (Zone III) with a seismic coefficient of 0.04g, indicating minimal risk of seismic events affecting project operations.

Vegetation and Land Use: The site has minimal tree cover, with scattered trees within the designated economic zone area. There are no forest lands in or around the proposed site. The majority of the area is currently utilized for agricultural activities, primarily cultivating paddy (Boro), reflecting the district's agricultural economy.

Air and Noise Quality: Air quality assessments conducted during baseline studies indicate satisfactory conditions with minimal threat of air pollution due to the rural nature of the area and limited industrial activities. Similarly, noise levels were reported to be within acceptable limits.

Water Resources: Groundwater is available at a depth of 800-1000 feet and is potable, indicating sufficient availability to meet the water demand of the proposed economic zone. Additionally, the Ghaga River flows adjacent to the site, approximately 0.3 km north of the proposed economic zone, providing an additional water resource.

Ecological Considerations: There are no protected areas, forest lands, or environmentally critical areas within a 10 km radius of the proposed site boundary, minimizing ecological impact.

Population and Livelihoods: The total population of the surrounding area, as recorded in the 2011 census, is approximately [insert population figure], with a low urbanization rate. The population is engaged in various agricultural activities, supplementing their incomes through fish farming, livestock rearing, and poultry.

Category	Subcategory	Data Sources	Primary Data Acquisition
Physical Environment	Meteorological and Climate Data	Bangladesh Meteorological Department (BMD)	Field surveys, data analysis
	Roads, Utilities, and Waste Disposal Facilities	NWRD of WARPO, CEGIS Archive	GIS database
	Natural Disasters	Bangladesh Water Development Board (BWDB)	Literature review, Field survey
Environmental Quality	Ambient Air Quality	Continuous Air Quality Monitoring Stations (CAMS), Department of Environment (DoE)	Continuous monitoring
	Ambient Noise Level	ANSI II Type Noise Meter	Noise monitoring
Physiography	Topography, Geology, and Soils	NWRD of WARPO archived in CEGIS, Field sampling & Lab analysis	Field sampling, Laboratory analysis
	Watershed, Hydrology, and Hydromorphology	BWDB, Bangladesh Inland Water Transport Authority (BIWT)	Remote sensing analysis, Field surveys
Land Resources	Land Use and Cover	CEGIS Archive	Image processing, classification
	Soil/Sediment	CEGIS Archive, Soil Resource Development Institute (SRDI) Database	Field sampling, Laboratory analysis at SRDI
Biological Environment	Flora and Fauna	Relevant reports, Wikipedia, Red Book of IUCN	Field surveys, Participatory Biodiversity Assessment
	Threatened and Endangered Species	Literature	Key Informant Interviews, Field survey
	Ecologically Sensitive Areas	Bangladesh Environment Conservation Act (BECA), 1995 and subsequent amendments	Field survey
Agriculture and Fisheries	Agriculture	Bangladesh Institute of Research and Training on Applied Nutrition (BIRTAN)	Remote Sensing (RS), Geographic Information System (GIS)

	Fisheries	Department of Fisheries (DoF)	Macro level catch survey, Focus Group Discussions
Biological Environment	Flora and Fauna	Relevant reports, Wikipedia, Red Book of IUCN	Field surveys
	Threatened and Endangered Species	Literature	Key Informant Interviews, Field survey

Table: Environmental Components

Surface Water Modeling:

For the proposed 2x660 MW diesel-based combined cycle power generation facility at Meghnaghat, Gazaria, Munshiganj, a comprehensive surface water modeling approach will be employed to assess surface water availability and dynamics within the project area. This modeling exercise plays a crucial role in understanding the hydrological cycle and ensuring sustainable water resource management.

Hydrological Model:

A hydrological model will be utilized to simulate the hydrological cycle of the area surrounding the project site. This model will incorporate various components such as precipitation, evapotranspiration, runoff, infiltration, and groundwater recharge to simulate the movement and distribution of surface water within the study area. By capturing the interactions between precipitation, land surface processes, and water flow, the hydrological model will provide insights into the surface water dynamics, including flow patterns, water storage, and recharge rates.

Map: Surface water

Morphological Assessment:

In the context of the proposed 2x660 MW diesel-based combined cycle power generation facility at Meghnaghat, Gazaria, Munshiganj, a morphological assessment of the nearby river systems will be conducted to understand the historical development and changes in morphological parameters, such as river width and bank lines. This assessment will provide critical insights into the dynamics of the river systems and their potential implications for the project.

Methodology:

Data Collection: Time series of satellite images covering the study area will be acquired from relevant sources, capturing historical changes in river morphology over time. These images will span multiple years to capture long-term trends in river behavior.

Image Analysis: Advanced image processing techniques will be employed to analyze the satellite images and extract morphological features of the river channels. This analysis will focus on identifying changes in river width, meander patterns, and bank lines over different time intervals.

Impact Assessment: The findings of the morphological assessment will be integrated into the overall Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA) process to assess potential impacts on the project. This includes evaluating risks related to riverbank erosion, changes in flood patterns, and alterations to water flow dynamics.

Figure: Flowchart showing the methodology of the morphological study

Land Use and Land Cover Assessment:

For the proposed 2x660 MW diesel-based combined cycle power generation facility at Meghnaghat, Gazaria, Munshiganj, a comprehensive assessment of existing land use patterns and land cover will be conducted. This assessment will be vital in understanding the current state of the project area and its surrounding environment, facilitating informed decision-making and environmental management strategies.

Figure: Flowchart of the Land use and Land Cover Analysis

Bio-Ecological Zone Assessment:

In the context of the proposed 2x660 MW diesel-based combined cycle power generation facility at Meghnaghat, Gazaria, Munshiganj, a comprehensive bio-ecological zone assessment will be conducted to evaluate the ecological characteristics and biodiversity of the project location. This assessment aims to identify and understand the various ecosystems, vegetation types, aquatic resources, and wildlife habitats present within the project area.

Methodology:**Data Collection:**

Available data from the CEGIS (Center for Environmental and Geographic Information Services) database will be utilized to prepare a map of the bio-ecological zones within the project area.

Information on bio-ecological zones and their characteristics will be collected from publications of the International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN) and other relevant organizations.

Ecological Structure and Function:

An analysis of the structure and function of terrestrial and aquatic ecosystems within the project location will be conducted. This will include assessing the composition, diversity, and interactions of biotic and abiotic components.

Vegetation and Floral Diversity:

The vegetation cover and floral diversity of the project area will be assessed, including the identification of dominant plant species, vegetation types, and ecosystem services provided by the flora.

Fish and Aquatic Resources:

The abundance, diversity, and health of fish and other aquatic resources in rivers, wetlands, and water bodies within the project area will be evaluated. This will involve assessing habitat suitability, water quality, and potential impacts on aquatic ecosystems.

Wildlife Resources:

The presence, distribution, and diversity of wildlife species, including mammals, birds, reptiles, and amphibians, will be documented. Special attention will be given to identifying species of conservation concern and their habitats.

Assessment of Endangered or Threatened Species:

Endangered or threatened species, critical habitats, and migratory routes will be assessed to determine their presence within the project area. This will involve identifying key habitats and migration corridors essential for the survival of vulnerable species.

Habitat and Migratory Route Identification:

Habitats and migratory routes of wildlife species will be identified and assessed to understand their importance for biodiversity conservation. This will include mapping key habitats, nesting sites, and migration pathways.

Socio-Economic Resources Assessment:

For the proposed 2x660 MW diesel-based combined cycle power generation facility at Meghnaghat, Gazaria, Munshiganj, a comprehensive assessment of socio-economic resources will be conducted to understand the demographic, economic, and social characteristics of the project area. This assessment aims to identify and evaluate the various socio-economic factors that may be impacted by the project's development.

Data Collection and Sources:

The socio-economic data for the project area will be collected from a variety of sources, including:

Government Agencies: Data on population demographics, employment, income levels, education, healthcare, and infrastructure will be obtained from relevant government agencies such as the Bangladesh Bureau of Statistics (BBS), Ministry of Planning, and Ministry of Health.

Local Authorities: Information on local governance structures, community development initiatives, and socio-economic indicators specific to the project area will be gathered from local authorities, including municipal offices and union councils.

Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs): Reports and studies conducted by NGOs working in the project area will provide insights into social welfare programs, poverty alleviation efforts, and community development projects.

Academic Institutions: Research papers, surveys, and studies conducted by academic institutions will contribute valuable socio-economic data, including trends, patterns, and challenges related to the local population and economy.

Community Consultations: Direct engagement with local communities through focus group discussions (FGDs), interviews, and participatory rural appraisals (PRAs) will allow for firsthand insights into community needs, aspirations, and socio-economic dynamics.

Key Socio-Economic Factors:

The socio-economic resources assessment will focus on the following key factors:

Demographic Profile: Population size, distribution, growth rate, age structure, and gender composition of the local population.

Economic Activities: Primary, secondary, and tertiary economic sectors, including agriculture, industry, services, and informal livelihoods.

Income Levels: Average household income, income distribution, poverty incidence, and access to financial services.

Employment Opportunities: Types of employment, unemployment rates, labor force participation, and job opportunities within the project area.

Education and Healthcare: Access to education and healthcare facilities, literacy rates, school enrollment, and health indicators such as maternal and child health outcomes.

Infrastructure: Availability and quality of infrastructure including transportation networks, electricity, water supply, sanitation, and communication services.

Social Services: Provision of social services such as welfare programs, social security schemes, and support for vulnerable populations including women, children, and the elderly.

Stakeholder Engagement and Consultation Plan:

For the proposed 2x660 MW diesel-based combined cycle power generation facility at Meghnaghat, Gazaria, Munshiganj, a comprehensive stakeholder engagement and consultation plan will be implemented to ensure the involvement of all relevant stakeholders throughout the project lifecycle. This plan aims to facilitate meaningful dialogue, gather valuable insights, and address concerns and suggestions raised by various stakeholders.

1. Focus Group Discussions (FGDs):

A series of FGDs will be conducted with specific groups representing diverse interests and perspectives within the project area. These discussions will provide a platform for stakeholders to express their views on the proposed project, discuss potential impacts and concerns, and offer suggestions for project planning and implementation. Occupational groups, vulnerable populations, and homogenous interest groups will be targeted for participation in these discussions.

2. Social Survey:

A household-level survey will be conducted in the study area to gather quantitative data on various socio-economic indicators. The survey will cover households located within a 1km radius of the project site and will collect information on demographics, landholding, education, and other relevant factors. This survey will provide valuable insights into the socio-economic profile of the local community and inform project planning and implementation strategies.

3. Public Consultation/ Disclosure Meetings:

Midway Consultation Meeting: A large public consultation meeting will be organized midway through the study project, bringing together key stakeholders including government officials, local government representatives, community leaders, and associations. Prior to the meeting, a stakeholder analysis will be conducted to identify and map important stakeholders at different levels. The consultation meeting will provide an opportunity to discuss project progress, share information, address concerns, and gather feedback from stakeholders.

Final Disclosure Workshop: At the end of the study project, a public disclosure or dissemination workshop will be organized to present the study findings and conclusions to stakeholders. The workshop will include presentations on the study methodology, key findings, and recommendations, followed by open discussions and Q&A sessions. Stakeholders will have the opportunity to provide final comments and feedback on the study findings, which will be incorporated into the final report.

8. Location and Land Use Analysis for the Proposed 2x660 MW Diesel-Based Combined Cycle Power Generation Facility:

The proposed project site spans approximately 201.83 acres and is strategically situated in Meghnaghat, Gazaria, Munshiganj, within the Dhaka division of Bangladesh. This selection is based on meticulous considerations of accessibility and proximity to key transportation networks, pivotal for the efficient establishment and operation of the power generation facility.

Location Details:

Geographical Positioning: Specifically situated in Meghnaghat, Gazaria, Munshiganj, within the Dhaka division of Bangladesh, the project site benefits from its central location within the region.

Map: Gazaria, Munshiganj

Map: Gazaria, Munshiganj

9. Potential Significant Impact Assessment:

The environmental and social assessment for the proposed 2x660 MW diesel-based combined cycle power generation facility will adhere to a systematic approach, meticulously analyzing the alterations in the surrounding environment induced by the project. This comprehensive assessment will entail comparing these changes with the baseline condition to ascertain their overall significance. By employing quantitative measures whenever feasible, the assessment will meticulously predict and evaluate both the direct and indirect positive and negative impacts of the project on the physical, biological, and socioeconomic aspects within the project's area of influence (AoI).

Methodology Overview:

Systematic Approach: The assessment will adopt a structured methodology, systematically analyzing changes in the environment and society brought about by the project. This approach ensures a thorough examination of potential impacts, considering both short-term and long-term implications.

Quantitative Analysis: Wherever possible, the assessment will employ quantitative measures to assess the magnitude of impacts, providing a clear understanding of their extent and significance.

Data Availability and Reliability: The assessment will evaluate the availability and reliability of data, identifying key data gaps and uncertainties related to impact predictions. Efforts will be made to fill these gaps through additional data collection or expert consultation.

Transboundary and Cumulative Impacts: The assessment will explore potential transboundary and cumulative impacts, recognizing that environmental and social changes may extend beyond the immediate project area and accumulate over time.

10. Mitigation and Abatement Measures:

In alignment with international best practices and the World Bank's Environmental and Social Standard (ESS) framework, a comprehensive set of mitigation and abatement measures will be implemented to address any negative impacts identified during the Environmental and Social Impact Assessment (ESIA) of the proposed 2x660 MW diesel-based combined cycle power generation facility. These measures will aim to mitigate adverse effects on the environment, ecology, and local communities, while also exploring opportunities for enhancement wherever feasible.

Mitigation Hierarchy Approach:

The mitigation measures will adhere to the Mitigation Hierarchy approach, as recommended by the World Bank's ESS framework. This approach prioritizes actions in the following sequence:

Avoidance: Measures will be identified to avoid or minimize adverse impacts wherever possible. This may include modifications to project design or operational practices to mitigate potential harm to the environment and communities.

Restoration: Efforts will be made to restore affected areas to their original state or to an equivalent condition. This may involve habitat restoration, reforestation, or other remediation activities to offset any damage caused by the project.

Offset Measures: Where avoidance and restoration are not feasible, offset measures will be implemented to compensate for any residual impacts. This may include investments in conservation projects or community development initiatives aimed at providing tangible benefits to affected communities and ecosystems.

Comprehensive Impact Assessment:

The ESIA study will quantify the cumulative impact of various pollutants, including air pollutants, noise, water pollutants, soil contaminants, and effluents, at sensitive locations within the project area. This assessment will inform the selection of appropriate mitigation measures tailored to address specific environmental and social concerns.

Ecological and Social Considerations:

In addition to addressing physical environmental impacts, the ESIA study will also prioritize ecological and social issues to ensure their proper consideration. Measures will be proposed to mitigate impacts on biodiversity, ecosystem services, and local communities, taking into account the unique socio-cultural context of the project area.

Figure: Mitigation Hierarchy

11. Residual Impact Assessment:

Following the implementation of mitigation measures, potential residual impacts that may affect the local community, surrounding environment, or economic activity will be diligently identified and categorized into construction and operational impacts. The Environmental and Social Impact Assessment (ESIA) team will employ a robust approach, utilizing expert judgment, consultations, and recommendations from stakeholders to identify and assess these residual impacts at various phases of the project implementation.

Identification of Residual Impacts:

Construction Phase Impacts: The ESIA team will scrutinize the potential residual impacts arising from construction activities such as land clearing, excavation, transportation, and infrastructure development. These may include temporary disturbances to ecosystems, increased noise levels, air pollution from construction machinery, and disruptions to local communities.

Operational Phase Impacts:

During the operational phase, residual impacts may manifest in the form of ongoing emissions, noise pollution, traffic congestion, and changes in land use patterns. The ESIA team will assess the potential long-term implications of these factors on the environment, community health, and economic activities in the vicinity of the project site.

12. Environmental Management Plan (EMP):

The Environmental and Social Impact Assessment (ESIA) study will outline a comprehensive Environmental Management Plan (EMP) encompassing a range of mitigation and management measures designed to avoid, reduce, mitigate, or compensate for any adverse environmental impacts associated with the proposed 2x660 MW diesel-based combined cycle power generation facility. Priority will be given to avoiding impacts wherever feasible, with mitigation measures tailored to address impact-specific concerns. The EMP will be formulated to facilitate easy implementation by the responsible agency while effectively addressing the collective environmental and social issues of the study area.

Key Components of the EMP:

Environmental and Social Management Plans (ESMP):

The EMP will include impact-specific Environmental and Social Management Plans (ESMP) for areas such as air quality, noise level, and water quality. These plans will outline specific actions and measures to mitigate impacts and ensure compliance with relevant regulations and standards.

Site-Specific Management Plans:

Site-specific ESMP will be developed for construction sites and special locations within the project area. These plans will address specific environmental and social considerations unique to each location, ensuring effective management and mitigation of potential impacts.

Special Management Plans:

Special ESMP will cover aspects such as grievance redress mechanisms, ecosystem management plans, and green belt management plans. These plans will address broader environmental and social concerns beyond the immediate project site, promoting holistic management and sustainability.

Environmental Code of Practice:

An Environmental Code of Practice will be incorporated into the EMP, providing guidelines and standards for environmentally responsible practices throughout the project lifecycle.

Mitigation Measures:

Mitigation measures will be outlined for different phases of the project cycle, including pre-construction, land development, and operation. Each mitigation measure will be described in detail, specifying the type of impact it addresses and the conditions under which it is required, such as continuous implementation or during contingencies.

Responsible Implementing Agencies:

The responsible implementing agencies for each mitigation measure will be identified, ensuring clear accountability and effective coordination in the implementation of the EMP.

Summary of Anticipated Impacts and Risks:

Anticipated significant adverse environmental impacts and risks will be identified and summarized, providing a comprehensive overview of potential challenges and concerns associated with the project.

Interlinkages and Integration:

The EMP will establish links to any other required mitigation plans, such as those related to involuntary resettlement or cultural heritage preservation, ensuring seamless integration and coordination of mitigation efforts across various sectors and disciplines.

13. Monitoring and Follow-Up Plan:

A robust environmental monitoring and follow-up plan will be developed at the conclusion of the Environmental and Social Impact Assessment (ESIA) study to ensure effective oversight and management of environmental aspects throughout the project lifecycle. This plan will adhere to the guidelines outlined in the International Finance Corporation (IFC) Guidelines, incorporating best practices for monitoring parameters aligned with project activities.

Key Elements of the Monitoring Plan:**Monitoring Parameters and Technical Specifications:**

The monitoring plan will provide a detailed description of monitoring measures, including technical specifications such as parameters to be measured, methods employed, sampling locations, frequency of measurements, detection limits, and definition of thresholds indicating the need for corrective actions. Parameters will be selected based on their relevance to project activities and potential environmental impacts.

Monitoring and Reporting Procedures:

The plan will outline monitoring and reporting procedures to ensure early detection of conditions requiring specific mitigation measures. These procedures will document the progress and outcomes of mitigation efforts, facilitating timely response and adaptive management. Clear protocols will be established for data collection, analysis, and reporting to relevant stakeholders.

Technical Guidance on Monitoring:

Parameters to Monitor: The plan will specify parameters relevant to air quality, water quality, noise levels, soil health, biodiversity, and other environmental factors impacted by project activities.

Measurement Methods: Appropriate measurement methods and techniques will be identified for each parameter, ensuring accuracy and reliability of data collection.

Sampling Locations: Sampling locations will be strategically determined to capture potential impacts, considering proximity to project activities and sensitive receptors.

Frequency of Measurements: The frequency of monitoring activities will be established based on project phases, potential impacts, and regulatory requirements. Regular monitoring will enable continuous assessment of environmental conditions and early identification of deviations from established thresholds.

Thresholds and Corrective Actions: Thresholds indicating the need for corrective actions will be defined for each monitored parameter. Clear guidelines will be provided for implementing corrective measures in response to exceedances of these thresholds.

Facilitating Timely Response and Documentation:

The monitoring plan will facilitate timely response to environmental conditions requiring corrective actions while documenting the effectiveness of mitigation measures implemented. By providing comprehensive guidance on technical aspects of monitoring, reporting, and response, the plan will ensure transparency, accountability, and continual improvement in environmental management practices.

Conclusion:

The environmental monitoring and follow-up plan will serve as a critical tool for ongoing oversight and management of environmental aspects associated with the project. Through regular monitoring, timely reporting, and adaptive management, the plan will support the project's commitment to environmental sustainability and compliance with regulatory requirements.

14. Decommissioning Plan:

N/A: Not Applicable for this Project.